

**DYES DERIVED FROM ACENAPHTHENEQUINONE. PART VI.
2-(4-METHYL)-THIONAPHTHENEACENAPHTHYLENE-
INDIGOS.**

BY SISIR KUMAR GUHA.

A few vat dyes have been prepared by the condensation of 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene with acenaphthenequinone and its derivatives. The dyeing shades developed on cotton and on wool from these compounds have been compared with those obtained from 2-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos and its 5-methyl and 6-methyl derivatives. The effect of methyl group in the 4-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule of the parent compound is to lighten the colour. It has also been found that as far as the colour is concerned the 4-methyl compounds occupy an intermediate position between the 5-methyl and the 6-methyl derivatives, and the 5-methyl dyes possess the deepest shade. The microphotographs of the spectra of the dyes of the three series have been taken and the absorption maxima determined.

Of the four theoretically possible isomeric methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthenes, the 5-methyl and the 6-methyl derivatives (Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 541; Friedlander, 9, 589; Auwers and Thies, *Ber.*, 1920, 53, 2285) were condensed with various acenaphthenequinones respectively and some valuable vat dyes were obtained of the general formula (I, R=Me, R'=R''=H; R'=Me, R=R''=H) (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 682; 1936, 13, 94). It was observed that Martinet's rule (*Rev. Gen. Mat. Col.*, 1921, 26, 17) holds good in the acenaphthenequinone series also as far as the substitution of one Me group in the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule of 2-thionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigo is concerned.

(I)

In the present paper methylthionaphthene-acenaphthyleneindigos are

described of the general formula (I, $R''=Me$; $R=R'=H$) obtained by condensing 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (*Chem. Zentr.*, 1928, 99, I, 759; E. P. 279489; U. S. P. 28037) with acenaphthenequinone and its various derivatives.

7-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene has not been isolated and not described in literature although 7:7'-dimethylthioindigo is mentioned in D. P. 241910 (*cf.* Thorpe and Ingold, "Vat Colours", 1923, p. 129). So the preparation of the dyestuffs described here has enabled the author to make a complete study, up till now, of the influence of one Me substitution upon the colour of the parent dye, commercially known as Ciba Scarlet G which is so particularly important for printing, and its various derivatives when the methyl substitution occurs in the 4, 5 or 6 position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule (E. P. 344/08; U. S. P. 891690; G. P. 205377; Bezdik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 386; Staudinger, Goldstein and Schlenker, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1921, 4, 342; E. P. 20003/08; G. P. 213504; Mayer and Schönfelder, *Ber.*, 1922, 55, 2972; Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 423).

It has been observed from a comparison of the dyeing shades on wool and on cotton obtained from 2-thionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigo and its various methyl derivatives that the entrance of Me-group into the 6-position, *i.e.*, in the *para* position to carbonyl group of the parent dye, lightens the colour considerably and this "hypsochromic" effect is very prominent. Again the entrance of the same group in the 5-position *i.e.*, the *meta* position to CO-group of the parent dye has a marked deepening effect. The dyestuffs described here show that when the Me-group is introduced in the 4-position, *i.e.*, in the *ortho*-position to CO-group, the colour is again lightened, but these 4-methyl compounds are deeper in colour than those of the corresponding 6-methyl compounds in this series. So it is concluded that the lightening of colour of isomeric thioindigoid dyes is most marked when the Me-group is introduced into the 6-position and the deepening effect is quite prominent when it is introduced in the 5-position of the thionaphthene nucleus of the molecule as discussed in Martinet's rule.

The colours of the dyeings on wool and on cotton of the various methylthionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigos are given in Table I.

The absorption spectra of the substance of the three series, mentioned in Table I, have now been taken, the examination of which (Fig. 1, 2, 3 and 4) points out that the heads of the absorption bands in case of 5-methyl compounds are shifted much towards the red end of the spectrum; then

come the heads of the bands of the 4-methyl compounds and last are those of the 6-methyl compounds. This result is in quite harmony with what was realised qualitatively and described before. All the solutions examined were in xylene and the absorption spectra of these dyes have been considered in the visible part of the spectrum as the colours of the dyestuffs have to be judged only. The absorption spectra were taken by Messrs Adam Hilger's constant deviation spectrograph. The source of light was a straight filament and argon comparison was made use of. The microphotographs of the spectra were taken with the Zeiss microphotometer and the positions of the argon lines were marked.

These dyes like the isomeric 5-methyl and 6-methyl varieties were obtained easily in crystalline form. They develop lustre when rubbed, volatilise when heated strongly above their melting points. The mother compound, its chloro and bromo derivatives, when treated with strong sulphuric acid, produce deep bluish green solutions and the methoxy derivative gives rise to blue solution from which on the addition of water, the dyes are reprecipitated unchanged suitable for dyeing on wool from an acid bath. The colours of the vat obtained from them by alkaline hydrosulphite resemble those of the corresponding 6-methyl compounds. The dyeing shades on wool and on cotton have been fully developed in all the cases except the methoxy derivative, which in case of cotton only behaved towards the alkaline reducing agent in the same way as the isomeric dyes. The faint violet-red obtained with great difficulty in this case turned into faint pink by atmospheric oxidation. The dyes are all soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, xylene and chloroform.

It is interesting to note (*cf.* Table I) that in the case of the mother compound, its chloro- and bromo derivatives there is a systematic gradual rise of melting point as the Me-group in the thionaphthene nucleus in the molecule of 2-thionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigo is shifted from 4 to 5 and then to 6-position. But in the case of methoxy derivatives there is fall of m. p. in the 5-methyl compound and again rise in case of the 6-methyl derivative.

The 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene, utilised in this investigation, has been described in various Patents (*loc. cit.*) but nothing is recorded regarding appearance, melting point and solubility, which together with other details, have been mentioned in the experimental part.

TABLE I.

A—Acenaphthylene indigo.

Names of the compounds.	M.p.	Shades.		Absorption maxima.
		on wool	on cotton.	
2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-A	263°	Vermillion	Vermillion	4735 Å
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-A	265°-66°	Scarlet-red	Scarlet red	4985
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-A	305°	Vermillion	Vermillion	4622
2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-A	270°-71°	Red	Red	4750
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-A	284°-85°	Bright scarlet red	Deep scarlet red	4987
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-chloro)-A	297°	Vermillion	Vermillion	4655
2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-A	260°	Red	Red	4800
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-A	282°	Deep scarlet red	Deep scarlet red	4992
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(3'-bromo)-A	302°	Bright vermilion	Light red	4703
2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	Above 305°	Deep red	Faint pink	4810
2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	279°-80°	Deep red	Pink	4995
2-(6-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-A	300°	Deep red	Faint pink	4783

EXPERIMENTAL.

4-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene.—The diazotised solution of (5 g. of) aminotolunitrile ($\text{NH}_2 : \text{CN} : \text{Me} = 1:2:3$) (Gabriel and Thieme, *Ber.*, 1919, 82, 1082; Kenner and Witham, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, 119, 1458) was poured into a cooled aqueous solution of potassium xanthogenate (7 g.) containing anhydrous sodium carbonate (14 g.) and the solution stirred; the sulphur-yellow crystalline precipitate, which first appeared was quickly transformed into a brown tarry mass with evolution of nitrogen. When the brown product became solid after standing, it was dissolved in hot sodium hydroxide (35%) and a little water; the resulting solution was heated at 100° on the water-bath with sodium monochloroacetate (5 g.). By acidification 3-methylbenzene-1-thioglycollic-2-carboxylic acid nitrile was obtained. It

was collected and as indicated in E. P. (*loc. cit.*) it was converted into the blue crystalline sodium salt of 3-methylbenzene-1-thioglycollic-2-carboxylic acid, cooled and strongly acidified with hydrochloric acid and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene was distilled in steam without preliminary heating. It solidifies to white needles and is quite pure for further use, m. p. 75-76°. It gradually turns on exposure to air brown-red but still it retains the property of oxythionaphthene. It remains unchanged in vacuum. It is soluble in pyridine, benzene nitrobenzene, aniline, acetic acid, amyl alcohol, acetone, chloroform, ether and is soluble in concentrated sulphuric acid with a light yellowish green colour. It crystallises from amyl alcohol in beautiful foliated needles.

The indigoid dyes described were obtained in a way similar to the isomeric 5-methyl and 6-methyl derivatives (Guha, *loc. cit.*). They were all purified by boiling with alcohol in which they are sparingly soluble and finally crystallised.

2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphtheneacenaphthyleneindigo—It was prepared from acenaphthenequinone (0.546 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in glacial acetic acid (55 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.). The thin needle-shaped crystalline dye (0.766 g.) was collected, purified and crystallised from acetic acid in bright silky vermilion colour, m. p. 263°. It is soluble in benzene, toluene, amyl alcohol and acetic acid. It dyes cotton in vermilion shades from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat and wool in the same colour from an acid bath. (Found : S, 9.77. $C_{21}H_{12}O_2S$ requires S, 9.75 per cent). *2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'(3'-chloro)-acenaphthyleneindigo* separated from 3-chloroacenaphthenequinone (0.6495 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.492 g.) in glacial acetic acid (65 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (4 c.c.) as red small thread-like needles which after being washed with acetic acid and hot water were crystallised from nitrobenzene, m. p. 270-71° (with previous shrinking). It is soluble in benzene, difficultly soluble in acetic acid. It dyes cotton from an alkaline vat in red shades and wool in the same colour from an acid bath. (Found : Cl, 9.49. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2ClS$ requires Cl, 9.79 per cent).

2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'(3'-bromo)-acenaphthyleneindigo was obtained from 3-bromoacenaphthenequinone (0.522 g.) and the methylhydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in the same quantity of acetic acid and hydrochloric acid as used in the formation of the foregoing substance. The red crystalline precipitate (0.429 g.) was crystallised in the same way and it possesses properties similar to the preceding compound. It melts at 260°. The dyeing shades on cotton and on wool are similar to the last

named compound but slightly deeper. (Found : Br, 19'24. $C_{21}H_{11}O_2BrS$ requires Br, 19'65 per cent).

2-(4-Methyl)-thionaphthene-8'-(1'-methoxy)-acenaphthyleneindigo.—It was prepared from β -methoxyacenaphthenequinone (0'636 g.) and 4-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0'492 g.) in acetic acid (120 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c. c.). The dye (0'5265 g.) was crystallised from pyridine in fine hair like needles not melting below 305° . It is difficultly soluble in benzene and acetic acid. It dyes cotton in faint pink colour from an alkaline vat and wool in deep red shades from an acid bath. (Found : S, 9'33. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 8'93 per cent).

My thanks are due to Mr. K. Prasad and Dr. A. C. Sircar for taking interest in this work and to Messrs D. K. Bhattacharya and B. N. Ghosh for helping me readily with spectrograph and microphotometer.

FIG. 1.

Curves 1—3 refer respectively to 2-(4-methyl)-, 2-(5-methyl) and 2-(6-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigos; corresponding exposure being (1) $17''$, (2 a) $15''$, (2 b) $20''$ and (3 a) $10''$, (3 b) $15''$.

